

Spelling annotated dictionary based on latin script.

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02.09.1993 The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 931-XII "On the introduction of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script" was adopted. Based on the positive experience of 1929-1940, when the Uzbek script was transferred to the Latin alphabet based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this Law was intended to serve to create favorable conditions for the acceleration of the republic's all-round development and entry into the world communication system, taking into account the wishes expressed by representatives of the general public. . In fact, the far-sighted decision is bearing fruit today, and the implementation of Latin graphics helps our young people learn foreign languages based on Latin script, as can be seen in real life examples, because today the alphabet of more than 70 countries is based on Latin script.

In the conditions of integration into the world community and the globalization of social processes, the rapid development of information and communication technologies has increased the attention to the state language, which is considered one of the most important values of our nation, which shows the spirituality, spirit and value of the nation, and which is an important factor.

Large-scale reforms in the field of introduction of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script in our country are primarily aimed at increasing the literacy of the general public, especially young people.

In addition, in the era of wide introduction of information technologies to all aspects of our life, such as water and air, and increasing the efficiency of their use, a number of positive results are being achieved in this field in our country. For this reason, the demand and need for a wider acquaintance with concepts in the field of information technologies is increasing.

According to the world experience, it is important to apply the latest achievements of science and technology in the process of improving the literacy of society's citizens, introducing innovative methods into public life in the environment of information and communication technologies.

"On May 15, 2018, the Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the "Action Plan for the wide introduction and further improvement of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script" until 2021. On the basis of this strategy, by the end of 2020, it is indicated that legal mechanisms should be developed to ensure that by the end of 2020, the operation of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script of the printed and electronic media will be fully ensured, and that the legal requirements related to this issue will be fulfilled unconditionally.

On this basis, many scientific researches and projects on the enrichment and improvement of the Uzbek language are being carried out in our country, dictionaries and scientific treatises on various fields are regularly published. At the moment, all the publishing houses in our country are publishing publications that show the charm of our native language.

Today, the young generation who started learning the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script has turned 23 years old. Most of the fundamental scientific, artistic, political and other literature remained in Cyrillic. As a result, most of the young people are limited in their opportunities during this exciting phase of life, when the need and passion for learning is born. It is necessary to solve these problems together with the general public. With the exchange of the alphabet, the need to convert our large scientific and cultural

heritage funds from Cyrillic to Latin has become an urgent issue today, so that many printed publications published in the last century would not become unnecessary.

The "IMLOMANBAI.UZ" website, which is the only one of its kind in our country, serves as an effective tool in solving the above-mentioned problems and improving the literacy of the general public.

Within the framework of this project, the political, social and economic reforms implemented by the president of our republic and our government in various fields, as well as the Strategy of Actions for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 The five priority directions of the development of the Republic and the implementation of the comprehensive programs implemented within the framework of the State program "Year of supporting active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies", the analysis of the information position of the population, and the implementation of the measures to provide them with the necessary and quick information are the main measures of the project. is the goal.

In order to implement these activities, the initiative group of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies plans to use the Internet and information communication tools to increase the literacy of citizens:

- forming a system of innovative ideas in the social, cultural, spiritual and educational development of the information society and democratic state in our republic;
- creation of a database of spelling and explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language in Latin script;
- development of comprehensive measures to increase the literacy potential of citizens in the context of informationalization of the society;
- complete completion and presentation to the general public of the easy-to-use "IMLOMANBAI.UZ" website, which contributes to the improvement of citizens' literacy in Latin script.

First of all, a working group consisting of teachers and talented students of TATU will be formed to implement the project of the IMLOMANBAI.UZ website, which includes the spelling and explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language in Latin script.

At the same time, the working group will prepare a perfect project strategy for the IMLOMANBAI.UZ website.

To implement the project, it is planned to conduct trainings, to provide them with a special room and necessary technical equipment for their free activities.

The idea of the "IMLOMANBAI.UZ" website project, which will be placed on the Internet for the use of the general public, and will be created on the basis of the spelling and explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language in Latin script, which is currently the only one of its kind, Who?, Where?, How? and why? within the framework of the principle, it is intended to serve the implementation of the following measures of literacy improvement:

1. Who? Identifying the target audience of the general public, all legal entities and individuals, all consumers in the republic;
2. Where? In the national information field, in particular, in social networks, websites and forums, in translating fundamental scientific, artistic, political and other literature into Latin script, in keeping working documents;
 - to prevent errors that may be found in advertising texts, banners, various announcements and signs in Uzbek;
3. How? Providing a user-friendly interface, various additional functions;
4. Why? Implementation of mechanisms for improving literacy.

Today, in our country there is no electronic system of spelling and explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language in the Latin script, therefore this project aims to

eliminate the spelling mistakes made in the Latin script of the Uzbek language in our daily life, to increase the status of the Uzbek language, as well as to search for rhyming words for young lovers of literature and poetry, Uzbek acts as a reliable assistant for language learners in determining whether they know words. By the end of 2020, legal mechanisms have been developed to ensure that the operation of print and electronic mass media in the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script is fully ensured and that the legal requirements related to this issue are fulfilled.

"IMLOMANBAI.uz" electronic spelling and explanatory online program created in this context is a timely program that is useful in performing the above-mentioned tasks, and it is important for all representatives of the Uzbek language spelling and Uzbek language. covers the explanation of the Uzbek words.

The program interface is simple, user-friendly. There is also a mobile application of the program, which creates more convenience for users. The hosting protection is very strong, the site itself is encrypted. The site database is backed up every week, so data is not lost.

A list of synonyms and antonyms is planned to be included in the future.

I plan to enrich the site by adding many more words spelling, explanation and rhyming.

I left my Facebook page for you to write your thoughts and opinions. You can contact me on Facebook. This resource was created using the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language.

Z.M. Ma'rufov (edited by).

Information about the planned use of project results by partners in the implementation of their economic activities, including the method of use, intentions to introduce new or improve products (goods, works, services), new or improved applied technologies based on the predicted results of the project; on the formation, following the results of the implementation of the project, of scientific and technological groundwork that ensures economic growth and social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan (with the attachment of supporting documents, if available)

– all members of the scientific team (including the project manager) satisfy paragraphs 6, 7, 13 of the tender documentation;

– for the entire period of project implementation, the project manager will be in an employment relationship with the organization, while the employment contract will not be an agreement on remote work

- the project is not similar in content to the project simultaneously submitted to competitions of scientific foundations and other organizations;

- the project does not contain information constituting a state secret or related to other information of limited access protected in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

– in due time will submit to the Ministry annual reports on the implementation of the project and on the intended use of the grant funds;

– will annually hold a school of young scientists on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the subject of the project, with the participation of at least five leading scientists as lecturers in each, as well as at least twenty young scientists under the age of 35 inclusive as listeners. Programs and reports on the events will be posted on the information and telecommunications network "Internet" on the organization's website;